

Traffic Prediction for The Intelligence Transportation System

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Abstract: *The aim is to develop a tool for predicting accurate and timely traffic flow information. Traffic environment involves everything that can affect the traffic flowing on the road, whether it's traffic signals, accidents, rallies, even repairing of roads that can cause a jam. Also, it helps in the future of autonomous vehicles. In the current decades, traffic data have been generating exponentially, and we have moved towards the big data concepts for transportation. The development and deployment of Intelligent Transportation System (ITSs) provide better accuracy for traffic flow prediction. To reduce the traffic congestion. To overcome the problem of traffic congestion, the system contains regression model and libraries like pandas, OS, NumPy, matplotlib, pyplot are used to predict the traffic. This has to be implemented so that the traffic congestion is controlled and can be accessed easily.*

Keywords: *Augmented reality, Graphical User Interface, AR virtual fitting room, Garment Model*

I. INTRODUCTION

Accurate real time information and traffic flow prediction are crucial components of such systems. ITS vary in technologies applied in; from advanced travel information systems, variable message signs, traffic signal control systems, to special user-friendly applications, such as travel advisors. The aim of all of these technologies is the same, to ease traffic flow, reduce traffic congestion and decrease travel time by advising drivers about their routes, time of departure, or even type of transportation.

The availability of large amounts of traffic related data, collected from a variety of sources and emerging field of sophisticated machine learning algorithms, has led to significant leap from analytical modelling to data driven modelling approach. The main concept of this paper is to investigate different machine learning algorithms and engineer features that would enable us predicting traffic state several prediction intervals into the future. The study of traffic forecasting is useful in mitigating congestion and making safer and cost-efficient travel. While traditional models use shallow networks, there will be exponential growth in many vehicles recently the traditional algorithms could not work in current scenarios.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Advanced vehicle guidance systems use real-time traffic information to route traffic and to avoid congestion. Unfortunately, these systems can only react upon the presence of traffic jams and not to prevent the creation of unnecessary congestion. Anticipatory vehicle routing is promising in that respect, because this approach allows directing vehicle routing by accounting for traffic forecast information. This paper presents a decentralized approach for anticipatory vehicle routing that is particularly useful in large-scale dynamic environments. The approach is based on delegate multiagent systems, i.e., an environment-centric coordination mechanism that is, in part, inspired by ant behaviour. Antlike agents explore the environment on behalf of vehicles and detect a congestion forecast, allowing vehicles to reroute. The approach is explained in depth and is evaluated by comparison with three alternative routing strategies. The experiments are done in simulation of a real-world traffic environment. The experiments indicate a considerable performance gain compared with the most advanced strategy under test, i.e., a traffic-message-channel-based routing strategy (Rutger et al.,2011) The trend of learning from videos instead of documents has increased. There could be hundreds and thousands of videos on a single topic, with varying degrees of context, content, and depth of the topic. The literature claims that learners are nowadays less interested in viewing a complete video but prefers the topic of their interests. This develops the need for indexing of video lectures. Manual annotation or topic wise indexing is not new in the case of videos. However, manual indexing is time-consuming due to the length of a typical video lecture and intricate storylines. Automatic indexing and annotation are, therefore, better and efficient solutions. This research aims to identify the need for automatic video indexing for better information retrieval and ease users navigating topics inside a video. The automatically identified topics are referred to as "Index Points." 137-layer YoloV4 Darknet Neural Network creates a custom object detector model. The model is trained on approximately 6000 video frames and then tested on a suite of 50 videos of around 20 hours of run time. Shot Boundary detection is performed using Structural Similarity fused with a Binary Search Pattern algorithm which outperformed the state-of-the-art SSIM technique by reducing the processing time to approximately 21% and providing around 96% accuracy. Generation of accurate index points in terms of true positives and false negatives is detected through precision, recall, and F1 score, which varies between 60-80% for every video. The results show that the proposed algorithm successfully generates a digital index with reasonable accuracy in topic detection (Marushi.,2021).

Number of vehicles at present and it's increasing dependency and not aware public increasing rate of traffic day by day. So, the paper focus to develop a tool for predicting correct and on time flow information. If we will have earlier facts of traffic,

causing things like, which affect the traffic flow, whether its traffic signals, accidents and rallies, even repairing work of which can cause a traffic, which is nearly correct then the rider can make decision according to it. The paper will help in the future of mechanized vehicles. The at one's fingertips forecast ways for traffic use some prediction models which are yet discontented to handle applications of real-world. So this motivate to work for traffic prediction problem build for traffic models, data available. The data generated or available on the transportation system is gigantic which makes difficult to predict traffic rightly. So, in this paper we have decided to use algorithms of machine learning and soft computing, deep learning to look over big-data for system of transportation with reduction in complication. For traffic signs identifications, image processing algorithms are used, which finally helps to automatic vehicles to do it well training

III. METHODOLOGY

Algorithm 1: For identifying the congested situation

1. Get the traffic data in every 5 min with details of: Location, Direction, Speed Start-End Junction
2. accumulate 5 min interval with the related data.
3. Calculate the gap between vehicle with all other vehicles within specified junction. If the gap is less than the specific distance, between two vehicles then those are observed to be the neighbourhood vehicles else, not considered as neighbour.

Algorithm 2: For classifying the traffic situation

1. This will give us the matrix.
2. Now give 1 to $A[i, j]$, if $A[i, j] < \text{threshold}$ then $A[i, j] = 1$ else $A[i, j] = 0$
3. Count $A[i, j] = 1$ and name i, j as neighbourhood vehicles.
4. Repeat above after every 5 min for 45 min
5. Plot the graph between neighbourhood vehicles and time interval.

If neighbourhood vehicles show an increasing graph then traffic is identified else no traffic Steps in implementation:

- a) Provide the GPS coordinates by the application.
- b) Execute the given algorithm.
- c) Evaluate matrix for dataset.
- d) Make split the dataset into training and testing.
- e) Examine discrete machine learning algorithms.
- f) Forecast 45 min interval through machine learning algorithm
- g) Conclude about the traffic Doing above steps we can apply the algorithm and we can obtain the model which gives the more correctness of the machine learning models than the existing. It is quite easy to teach the deep network by applying the BP methodology with the gradient-based development technique. Unfortunately, its notable that deep networks coached by this method have bad performance. So we have not included the deep learning models in the work. Following the proposed algorithm, we solved many of problems like big-data, also the huge dataset is reduced to avoid overflow of the model.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Prediction of traffic at different junction.

Junction 2 – blue Junction 3 – yellow

IV. CONCLUSION

Although deep learning and genetic algorithm is an important problem in data analysis, it has not been dealt with extensively by the ML community. The proposed algorithm gives higher accuracy than the existing algorithms. It improves the complexity issues throughout the dataset. Also, we have planned to integrate the web server and the application. The things algorithms will be further improved to much higher accuracy. The data split training and testing, as 97% of the dataset was applied for training and 3% for testing. We have divided our work into three parts: The first part, which consists of Random-forest classifier, Decisiontree classifier and as well as SVM for the dataset.

REFERENCES

- [1]. A. Mohite and A. Acharya, "Blockchain for government fund tracking using hyperledger," in International Conference on Computational Techniques, Electronics and Mechanical Systems (CTEMS), 21-22 Dec., 2018.
- [2]. T. A. Syed, A. Alzahrani, S. Jan, M. S. Siddiqui, A. Nadeem, and T. Alghamdi, "A comparative analysis of blockchain architecture and its applications: Problems and recommendations," 04 December 2019.
- [3]. Blockchain challenges and opportunities: A survey, booktitle=International Journal of Web and Grid Services, Volume 14, No. 4, author=Zibin Zheng and Shaoan Xie and HongNing Dai and Xiangping Chen and Huaimin Wang, year=2018,"
- [4]. R. Chatterjee and R. Chatterjee, "An overview of emerging technology: Blockchain," in 3rd International Conference on Computational Intelligence and Networks (CINE), 28 Oct., 2017.
- [5]. H. R. Andrian, N. B. Kurniawan, and S. bah, "Blockchain technology and implementation: A systematic literature review," in 2018 International Conference on Information Technology Systems and Innovation (ICITSI), 22-26 Oct, 2018.
- [6]. Hye-Young Paik 1, XIWEI XU 1, H. M. N. D. B. 1, S. U. L. 3, and Sin Kuang Lo 1, "Application of data management in blockchain-based systems: From architecture to governance," in IEEE Access PP (99):1-1, Volume 7, 2019.
- [7]. M. Dabbagh, M. Sookhak, and N. S. Safa, "The evolution of blockchain: A bibliometric study," 29 January 2019.
- [8]. S. Singh and N. Singh, "Blockchain: Future of Financial and cyber security," in 2nd International Conference on Contemporary Computing and Informatics (IC3I), 4-17 Dec. 2016.
- [9]. S. Tikhomirov, "Ethereum: state of knowledge and research perspectives," in International Symposium on Foundations and Practice of Security, 206-221, 2017
- [10]. S. Zhai, Y. Yang, J. Li, C. Qiu, and J. Zhao, "Research on the application of cryptography on blockchain," in Journal of Physics: Conference Series, Volume 1168

REFERENCES

- Fei-Yue Wang et al. Parallel control and management for intelligent transportation systems: Concepts, architectures, and applications. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 2010.
- Yongchang Ma, Mashrur Chowdhury, Mansoureh Jeihani, and Ryan Fries. Accelerated incident detection across transportation networks using vehicle kinetics and support vector machine in cooperation with infrastructure agents. *IET intelligent transport systems*, 4(4):328–337, 2010.
- Rutger Claes, Tom Holvoet, and Danny Weyns. A decentralized approach for anticipatory vehicle routing using delegate multiagent systems. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 12(2):364–373, 2011.
- Mehul Mahrishi and Sudha Morwal. Index point detection and semantic indexing of videos - a comparative review. *Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing, Springer*, 2020.
- Joseph D Crabtree and Nikiforos Stamatidis. Dedicated short-range communications technology for freeway incident detection: Performance assessment based on traffic simulation data. *Transportation Research Record*, 2000(1):59–69, 2007.
- H Qi, RL Cheu, and DH Lee. Freeway incident detection using kinematic data from probe vehicles. In *9th World Congress on Intelligent Transport Systems ITS America, ITS Japan, ERTICO (Intelligent Transport Systems and Services-Europe)*, 2002.
- Z. Zhao, W. Chen, X. Wu, P. C. Y. Chen, and J. Liu. Lstm network: a deep learning approach for short-term traffic forecast. *IET Intelligent Transport Systems*, 11(2):68–75, 2017.
- C. Zhang, P. Patras, and H. Haddadi. Deep learning in mobile and wireless networking: A survey. *IEEE Communications Surveys Tutorials*, 21(3):2224–2287, thirdquarter 2019.
- Chun-Hsin Wu, Jan-Ming Ho, and D. T. Lee. Travel-time prediction with support vector regression. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 5(4):276–281, Dec 2004.
- Yan-Yan Song and LU Ying. Decision tree methods: applications for classification and prediction. *Shanghai archives of psychiatry*, 27(2):130, 2015.
- Yiming He, Mashrur Chowdhury, Yongchang Ma, and Pierluigi Pisu. Merging mobility and energy vision with hybrid electric vehicles and vehicle infrastructure integration. *Energy Policy*, 41:599–609, 2012.